

The Training and Support Needs of Faculty And Students Using A Health Information Technology System Were Significant: A Case Study in a Dental School

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Abstract

Health Information Technology Systems (HITS) are becoming more widely integrated into patient care in the dental school setting. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the impact of a chairside HITS on users in the dental school setting. Qualitative techniques, including interviews, focus groups and observations, were used. Using grounded theory, we saw 9 themes emerge. One theme of particular interest was that “training and support needs of end-users were significant.” This paper explores this theme in detail and discusses the implications.

Introduction

Dental schools across North America are integrating patient care components of HITS in their clinics. However, the impact of this integration on faculty and students is not well understood. We conducted a study to address how all HITS users were impacted by the integration of a system chairside.¹ Nine themes emerged: HITS benefits were disproportionate among users, communicating about the HITS was challenging, users experienced a range of strong emotions, the instructor persona diminished, there were shifts in the school’s power structure, allocation of end-users’ time shifted, the training and support needs of end-users were significant, perceived lack of HITS usability made documentation cumbersome, and clinicians believed their workflow was disrupted. The theme “the training and support needs of end-users were significant” is especially interesting because it is under the control of the institution and has the potential to greatly impact end-users perception and experience using the HITS. We will explore that theme in more detail here.

Methods

Below is a brief description of our methods; a more elaborate description has been published.¹

Site Selection and Description

This study was conducted in the Western School of Dentistry (a pseudonym) Department of Pediatric Dentistry 1 year after a big bang HITS implementation in their clinic, and 2 years into a schoolwide staggered implementation. In the dental setting HITS is a comprehensive term that includes the software and hardware of information systems used for patient care, administrative tasks, education and clinical research. The school used AxiUm (Exan, Port Coquitlam, Canada) the most common dental school HITS.

Participant Selection

We identified 4 user groups: administrators, HITS support staff, faculty (full and part-time) and students (third and fourth year predoctoral students and pediatric residents). We recruited the most experienced HITS users from each group. End-users were defined as faculty and students using the HITS for clinical care.

Data Collection and Analysis

To ensure internal validity, we used a triangulated data gathering approach and multiple analysts. From July through October 2007, the first author led, audio taped and transcribed 4 semi-structured interviews (8 hrs) and 4 focus groups (5 hrs). Comments were jotted down during observations of end-users using the HITS during clinical care and undergoing training (8 hrs). The data was entered into NVivo 8, a qualitative research software (QSR International, Victoria, Australia). The first author completed all line by line coding while all authors collaborated to identify the themes. The original 9 themes were generated using grounded theory.² For this paper, the 43 instances of “the training and support needs of end-users were significant” were analyzed using a process of axial coding.³

Results

We identified 4 subthemes concerning end-users' significant training and support needs: End-users' training and support needs require constant attention, lack of understanding of HITS deleteriously impacted end-users' experiences, HITS training competed for curricular time with clinical topics, and faculty had limited ability to meet students' support needs. Quotes from users were included in italics where the comments succinctly exemplified users' experience.

1. End-users' training and support needs required constant attention.

Although end-users were provided pre-clinical HITS training, the training alone was not sufficient to make them proficient. Student training involved a combination of class lectures, exercises with a mock patient's electronic record, and access to an organizational HITS manual while faculty training involved one-on-one sessions with a trainer and manual access. End-users found it challenging to translate what they learned in training into practice. Another hurdle was the ability to absorb the intricacies of the training all at one time, *"To remember [the training], I need to see it again and again."*

Being able to navigate the HITS well impacted patient care because the HITS was the source of all patients' information. End-users commented that learning the system was a continuous, iterative process and they depended on help from support staff, administrators and more experienced end-users to improve their use, and, furthermore, maximize the benefits of a HITS. Chairside support was provided by administrators and support staff the first few weeks of clinic and then tapered off as end-users became more comfortable in using the HITS. Faculty and students commented that they would appreciate having that high level of support available to them at all times in the clinics. When an administrator or support staff member was not available, end-users were likely to temporarily record the information on paper, ask a fellow end-user or attempt *"trial and error."*

Unlike paper charts, the HITS allowed constant monitoring of data quality across the department by the school's quality assurance team and the identification of individual and/or department-wide problems in data quality. In some situations, HITS re-

training was indicated. Retraining happened on an as needed basis and involved email alerts to faculty and students, presentations in available venues such as faculty meetings or classes, and more written instructions made available within the HITS. An administrator commented that routine retraining could be beneficial because areas of improvement are always being identified, and end-user understanding and questions about the HITS became more sophisticated with use. Furthermore, the system underwent periodic upgrades that required more end-user training and support.

2. Lack of understanding of HITS deleteriously impacted end-users' experiences.

End-users' limited training and support resulted in a lack of understanding that prevented unrealistic HITS expectations from being checked. It was common for end-users to think of the HITS as simply "replacing the paper chart" so they expressed surprise that the HITS integration into patient care required far reaching adjustments in how they delivered that care. The problems end-users identified revolved around software, hardware and workflow. Software concerns revolved around the wording of forms, screen formatting (font and partitioning), and rigid data entry options (list boxes, text boxes, etc.). Hardware issues included difficulty in using the small keyboard finger pad, the electronic card readers (which faculty used to approve student work) and the wall mounted workstations. For workflow issues, end-users focused on the limited HITS support available chairside, having to share centrally located hardware (signature pads and printers), entering data collected on a paper form, infection control of the workstation, and a lack of portability of the HITS. Faculty was especially aware of workflow issues around keeping abreast of the medical histories and treatment plans of the multiple patients their students oversaw in parallel.

End-users were overly optimistic that problems they associated with using the HITS were easily corrected. While administrators and support staff understood end-users' had concerns with the HITS and its impact on their workflow, they also were well aware of their limitations in resolving those issues. For school-wide operations and processes to work, it was not appropriate to personalize software feature for each end-user. This decision and limited

HITS hardware product options, funds, clinic space and time made modifying the HITS to each end-user's satisfaction impossible.

Users' limited HITS vocabulary made having a meaningful exchange about the HITS challenging. Except for the support staff, most users were familiar with computers but lacked any detailed understanding of hardware or software. Without a HITS vocabulary, everything having to do with the system was frequently lumped together under the name of one of the software vendors. In addition, end-users struggled with how to adequately articulate problems they encountered in integrating the HITS into patient care with each other and support staff.

3. HITS training competed for curricular time with clinical topics.

Faculty members commented that providing HITS training and support to students added another, sometimes burdensome, dimension to patient care and clinical instruction. Given the limited preclinical lecture time pediatric faculty had with predoctoral students, they were uneasy with taking time away from discussing patient care to cover the HITS. In the clinic, faculty wanted the focus of their time with students to be on caring for the patient, not using the system.

Administrators and faculty commented that it was unclear where, when and how HITS training could best be accomplished. Should HITS training be integrated into the preclinic laboratory or lectures, or conducted right before students begin working in the clinic? While official training was completed before clinic started, administrators noticed students took training more seriously once they were in the clinics. Should HITS training be stand-alone or integrated into the pediatric coursework? Should training occur one-on-one, in small groups, in the classroom, in the clinic, or all of these? Should training involve a manual, lectures, or work on mock patient scenarios? Manuals were available but rarely seen being used. Students were especially appreciative of mock patient scenarios completed in unison. However, this training technique seemed to be only part of the success equation. Many end-users stated that their understanding of the HITS only crystallized with in-clinic real patient experience.

4. Faculty had limited ability to meet students' support needs.

Administrators and faculty brought up the issue of "who could best support end-users?" Was it administrators who had a comprehensive understanding of the HITS and could focus on the system or faculty who could weave together patient care and the HITS? Clinic faculty members tended to draw a line between mentoring students in patient care versus the HITS, leaving the latter to the administration and support staff. Although administrators could empathize with faculty requests for additional expert HITS support, providing that level of support was a staffing challenge.

It was a daunting task for faculty and administrators to adequately unravel and bring together navigation of the HITS, clinic workflow and patient care in a format helpful to students. The science of HITS involves contributions from domains dentists are not traditionally schooled in: health care administration, computer science, biomedical engineering, informatics, information technology and information science. Similarly, administrators and HITS support staff that were more fluent in the aforementioned domains did not have the experience of providing patient care or supervising students in providing care. Administrators provided HITS training to students during dedicated sessions (independent of faculty) and faculty provided HITS training in combination with preclinical lectures and during clinic (independent of administrators and HITS support staff). During training and support conversations regarding the HITS, the faculty deferred to administrators/support staff, and administrators/support staff deferred to faculty regarding HITS issues that one group considered the other groups' domain. As a result, students had to integrate the separate domains themselves.

Discussion

This is the first study to qualitatively evaluate the impact of clinic HITS on dental students and faculty. We will discuss issues around successful HITS adoption, dental education and HITS training and support.

The challenge of producing and maintaining well-trained end-users is a recognized barrier to experiencing the maximum benefits of HITS integration

into patient care.^{4,6} In addition to our qualitative study, a survey of dental school end-users also identified training and support as an important issue in the dental setting.⁷ The survey of approximately 100 end-users' likes and dislikes found 30% of respondents liked that the system made them more productive (productivity itself was not evaluated). This response suggests a minority of end-users believed the system improved their efficiency over the paper predecessor. While a staggered or decreased productivity could be the result of the system itself, it could also reflect a need for more user training and support. A categorization of the end-users' free text "dislikes" of the HITS identified "support and training" (4%) as a minor issue. But, given the follow-up opportunity to provide suggestions how improvements could be made, a disproportionate 15% of the comments involved more training and support. Interestingly, the most common suggestion addressed improving "usability" (47%). The authors summarized end-users comments around usability as finding the system "confusing and/or difficult to use." We note that end-users' frustration with usability could potentially be resolved with more and/or better training and support.

A systematic review of Computerized Provider Order Entry adoption in the medical setting found its configuration has an impact on clinician adoption of the system.⁸ In our study we, too found there is a link between the configuration, HITS usability, and users' training and support needs. When users describe the function of the HITS as "duplicating paper" or "replacing paper" (common end-user comments), they do not do justice to the benefits the HITS could provide, and likewise, they may not understand, the impact a stationary, rigidly formatted, electronic information system can have on their work. HITS can improve and/or negatively impact how, what, where and when providers collect, find, view and synthesize information, compared to a traditional paper charts. While training and support can improve end-user skills with HITS, ultimately the success of end-users in using HITS depends on the systems' ability to support end-user's work.

End-users do not have a good grasp of the scientific underpinnings of HITS. Traditionally, dental education provides students with the scientific background necessary to understand oral diseases and

their management, as well as, mentoring them in their acquisition of the skills and techniques to provide oral health care. HITS training can also be broken down into two components: the science and the technical skills. HITS training tends to focus on the latter.

While end-users were trained in how to use the school's particular system, and competent at using it for their patient encounters, they were not able to relate their issues to the current challenges health care as a whole has in integrating HITS into patient care. End-users knew that in using the HITS they were part of a dramatic shift in how the profession documents care. Yet, they were not necessarily clear why HITS are "the future" (a common user sentiment) and how HITS could impact their ability to care for patients.

Incorporating the science of HITS into student training would provide them with the framework to better understand future advances in patient care made possible with HITS. It is well recognized that as biomedical science advances, health care will become more knowledge-based (information-tool dependent) and less task-based.⁹ As a result, dental practice will incorporate more sophisticated information technology into providing care.¹⁰ HITS has the potential to improve dentists' ability to provide efficient and effective patient care by offering methods to better track patients' health, provide personalized care (with access to relevant evidence and information support), assess patient outcomes, and contribute to practice-based research initiatives. When end-users have a basic understanding of the science of HITS they are better positioned to evaluate its benefits and limitations. As a result, dentists become wiser consumers who can contribute to the development of HITS that improve patient care.

The training and support needs of faculty and students, as well as strategies to meet those needs, are not well researched. A survey of the dental literature focused on the intersection of computers and professional education revealed it was limited in scope. Most papers in this area address issues around integrating and evaluating preclinic computer-assisted learning, implementing the evidence-based dentistry approach, assessing users' computer attitudes and literacy, and business decisions around HITS.¹¹⁻¹⁴ Although there are no studies comparing

dental end-user abilities, it has been suggested a “digital divide” exists between faculty and students. Many students have a higher comfort level with communication and information technology than faculty. Furthermore, students who need to use the system to provide patient care are more proficient than faculty who oversee these students. Of note, other professions have found that the discrepancy between faculty and student familiarity with HITS has produced a need for “reverse mentoring,” when students mentor faculty in HITS use.¹⁵ The idea that the student is more knowledgeable than the faculty member has the potential to be unsettling for both and perplexing to observing patients.

With increasing integration of HITS into patient care in dental schools and dental offices, the need for a unique expertise is becoming more evident. Twenty years ago the American Association of Dental Schools realized the growing use of dental information systems would require the creation of the new discipline “dental informatics”.¹⁶ Significant progress has been made in characterizing the discipline, and a small body of literature now exists.¹⁷⁻²⁴ More effort is needed to develop patient management strategies (e.g., HITS-assisted diagnosis and management of caries as an infectious disease), studies evaluating what and how information is best presented to assist the dentist in their work (e.g., synthesizing patient specific best evidence) and usability (e.g., integrating HITS interactions into dentists’ workflow). Other health care professions have comparable HITS goals and are evaluating methods to build critical masses of providers with expertise in informatics.^{25, 26}

Conclusion

With the integration of HITS into patient care, we identified a significant need among end-users for training and chairside support. How widespread the issue is among institutions and how to optimize end-user training and support requires more research. Finally, to maximize the potential that HITS have to support dentists’ ability to provide patient care, it is imperative that future dentists have an understanding of the science of HITS that allows them to think critically about these systems.

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